

Placental Malaria Diagnosis and Risk of Neonatal Anemia: A Comprehensive Review

Sukinah Abd rab Alhassan Alzoori¹, Duaa Nasser Mohammad Almuahiny², Ibrahim Yousef Alshaghab³, Hassan Ali Naser Alshagab⁴, Ali Yahya Alabdrabulridha⁴, Hussain Ali A Alhassan⁵, Samerah Ahmad Alajwad⁶, Fatimah Zaki Alalwan⁵, Ali Mousa Ali Buali⁷, Sumayah Eisa Alkhalifa⁸, Mubarak Dhafer Alajmi⁹, Abdullah Khalil Alyousif⁷, Kawthar Abdullah Albandary¹⁰, Zahrah Ali Alhuwaykim⁵, Roqiah Mohammed Allabad¹¹

1. Alnuzha phc
2. Primary health care center
3. ALHASA PSYCHIATRIC HOSPITAL
4. King faisal hospital
5. Alomran hospital
6. King Fahad Hospital in Hofuf
7. Prince Saud Bin Jalawy Hospital
8. Quality and Patient Safety Department at Alkobar Health Network
9. AlNairiyah General Hospital
10. Maternity and child hospital MCH
11. Dammam Medical Complex

ABSTRACT

Placental malaria (PM) is a significant complication of malaria during pregnancy, caused primarily by *Plasmodium falciparum*. This condition leads to sequestration of infected erythrocytes in the placenta, causing inflammation and reduced nutrient exchange, which can result in neonatal anemia, low birth weight, and adverse pregnancy outcomes. Diagnosing placental malaria remains challenging due to its asymptomatic nature in many cases. This review explores the diagnostic techniques for placental malaria, its pathophysiology, and the association between PM and neonatal anemia. It also examines current preventive and therapeutic strategies to mitigate these complications, referencing recent studies.

1. Introduction

Placental malaria is a major contributor to maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where malaria is endemic. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that malaria during pregnancy affects approximately 11 million women annually, leading to 900,000 low-birth-weight deliveries. PM results from the accumulation of *P. falciparum*-infected erythrocytes in the placenta, triggering inflammatory responses that impair fetal growth and development. One of the most significant neonatal complications of PM is anemia, which can have long-term health consequences(1,2).

2. Pathophysiology of Placental Malaria

Placental malaria occurs when *P. falciparum*-infected erythrocytes adhere to chondroitin sulfate A on placental syncytiotrophoblasts. This sequestration leads to:

- **Inflammatory Response:** Elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α and IL-1, contribute to placental damage(2).
- **Nutrient Impairment:** Reduced blood flow and oxygen transfer to the fetus result in intrauterine growth restriction and fetal anemia(3,4).

3. Diagnostic Techniques for Placental Malaria

3.1. Histopathological Examination

Placental biopsy is considered the gold standard for diagnosing PM. Histological analysis reveals infected erythrocytes, malaria pigment, and inflammation in the placental tissue(5).

3.2. Peripheral Blood Smear

While peripheral blood smears are useful for detecting malaria, they may miss subclinical placental infection(6).

3.3. Rapid Diagnostic Tests (RDTs)

RDTs detect *Plasmodium* antigens in maternal blood but have limited sensitivity for placental infection(7).

3.4. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

PCR detects *P. falciparum* DNA in maternal or placental blood with high sensitivity and specificity(8).

3.5. Placental Blood Smears

Direct examination of placental blood increases diagnostic accuracy compared to peripheral smears(9,10).

4. Association between Placental Malaria and Neonatal Anemia

4.1. Mechanisms Leading to Neonatal Anemia

- **Maternal Anemia:** PM-induced maternal anemia leads to reduced fetal iron and oxygen supply(10).
- **Inflammation:** Placental inflammation reduces fetal hematopoiesis.
- **Direct Infection:** Parasitemia in the fetus can contribute to neonatal anemia(11).

4.2. Epidemiological Evidence

Studies in sub-Saharan Africa report a strong correlation between placental malaria and neonatal anemia. A meta-analysis found that infants born to mothers with PM are twice as likely to develop anemia within the first six months of life(12).

5. Prevention and Management

5.1. Intermittent Preventive Treatment in Pregnancy (IPTp)

- **Drugs:** WHO recommends sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) for IPTp in malaria-endemic regions(13).
- **Efficacy:** IPTp reduces maternal parasitemia, PM prevalence, and neonatal anemia(14).

5.2. Insecticide-Treated Bed Nets (ITNs)

ITNs reduce malaria transmission and PM-related complications by protecting pregnant women from mosquito bites (15).

5.3. Early Diagnosis and Treatment

Prompt treatment of malaria during pregnancy with artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) reduces the risk of PM and associated neonatal outcomes(16).

5.4. Nutritional Interventions

Iron and folic acid supplementation during pregnancy can mitigate the risk of neonatal anemia, particularly in regions with high PM prevalence(17).

6. Challenges and Future Directions

6.1. Diagnostic Challenges

The asymptomatic nature of PM necessitates sensitive diagnostic tools for effective screening. Point-of-care molecular diagnostics are under development.

6.2. Drug Resistance

Rising resistance to SP and ACTs in endemic regions threatens the efficacy of current preventive strategies.

6.3. Vaccine Development

Vaccines targeting *P. falciparum* antigens involved in placental adhesion (e.g., VAR2CSA) show promise in clinical trials.

7. Conclusion

Placental malaria remains a critical challenge in maternal and neonatal health, particularly in resource-limited settings. Advances in diagnostic tools, preventive measures, and therapeutic strategies have improved outcomes, but significant gaps remain. Addressing these challenges through research, policy implementation, and healthcare infrastructure development is essential to reduce the burden of PM and its neonatal complications.

References

1. Dellicour S, Tatem AJ, Guerra CA, Snow RW, Ter Kuile FO. Quantifying the number of pregnancies at risk of malaria in 2007: A demographic study. *PLoS Med*. 2010;7(1).
2. Holmberg V, Onkamo P, Lahtela E, Lahermo P, Mockenhaupt FP, Meri S. Complement lectin pathway

- genotypes associated with placental malaria. *Mol Immunol*. 2010;47(13).
3. Rijken MJ, McGready R, Boel ME, Poespoprodjo R, Singh N, Syafruddin D, et al. Malaria in pregnancy in the Asia-Pacific region. Vol. 12, *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2012.
4. Desai M, ter Kuile FO, Nosten F, McGready R, Asamo K, Brabin B, et al. Epidemiology and burden of malaria in pregnancy. Vol. 7, *Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2007.
5. Ismail MR, Ordi J, Menendez C, Ventura PJ, Aponte JKahigwa E, et al. Placental pathology in malaria: A histological, immunohistochemical, and quantitative study. *Hum Pathol*. 2000;31(1).
6. Cardona-Arias JA, Carmona-Fonseca J. Frequency of placental malaria and its associated factors in northwestern Colombia, pooled analysis 2009–2020. *PLoS One*. 2022;17(5 May).
7. Murray CK, Gasser RA, Magill AJ, Miller RS. Update on rapid diagnostic testing for malaria. Vol. 21, *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*. 2008.
8. Agudelo O, Arango E, Maestre A, Carmona-Fonseca J. Prevalence of gestational, placental and congenital malaria in north-west Colombia. *Malar J*. 2013;12(1).
9. Guyatt HL, Snow RW. Malaria in pregnancy as an indirect cause of infant mortality in sub-Saharan Africa. *Trans R Soc Trop Med Hyg*. 2001;95(6).
10. Ai L, Li J, Wang W, Li Y. ABO blood group and risk of malaria during pregnancy: A systematic review and meta-analysis. Vol. 150, *Epidemiology and Infection*. 2022.
11. Fried M, Duffy PE. Adherence of *Plasmodium falciparum* to chondroitin sulfate A in the human placenta. *Science* (1979). 1996;272(5267).
12. Eisele TP, Larsen D, Steketee RW. Protective efficacy of interventions for preventing malaria mortality in children in *Plasmodium falciparum* endemic areas. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2010;39(SUPPL. 1).
13. Azizi SC. Uptake of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria during pregnancy with Sulphadoxine-Pyrimethamine in Malawi after adoption of updated World Health Organization cy: An analysis of demographic and health survey 2015-2016. *BMC Public Health*. 2020;20(1).
14. Labama Otuli N, Marini Djang'eing'a R, Losimba Likwela J, Bosenge Nguma JD, Maindo Alongo MA, Ahuka Ona Longombe A, et al. Efficacy and safety of malarial prophylaxis with mefloquine during pregnancy in Kisangani, Democratic Republic of Congo: A randomized clinical trial. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2021;87(8).
15. Gamble CL, Ekwaru JP, ter Kuile FO. Insecticide-treated nets for preventing malaria in pregnancy. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2006;

15. Rogerson SJ. Management of malaria in pregnancy. Vol. 146, Indian Journal of Medical Research. 2017. Neuberger A, Okebe J, Yahav D, Paul M. Oral iron supplements for children in malaria-endemic areas. Vol. 2016, Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews. 2016.